

ISSUES OF INTRODUCING NEW APPROACHES TO THE EDUCATION OF SOPHISTICATION BASED ON MUSICAL HERITAGE IN THE CONTINUOUS SPIRITUAL EDUCATION SYSTEM

Bakhtiyor Mirzarakhimov
Fergana State University

Associate Professor of the Department of Philosophy,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Orcid: 0000-0003-2241-6747

E-mail: alfargoniy.uz@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13704593>

ABSTRACT:

Development of artistic and aesthetic competence in young people in modern conditions as a complex social phenomenon, processes and results of aesthetic mastering of nature at the level of society, aesthetic conditions of work, life, social relations; a certain state of taste and interests; the effect of the theory and practice of aesthetic education is observed in the manifestation of their socio-aesthetic activity. Therefore, by developing the artistic and aesthetic knowledge and skills of future music education teachers, it will be possible to improve the professional competence of music education pedagogues in our country, to expand the worldview of understanding art, to develop their thinking, and through this, to achieve the reform of the system of developing musical thinking in students.

KEYWORDS:

Artistic, Aesthetic Competence, Musical Heritage, Refinement Education, Spiritual Education, Art, Aesthetic Consciousness

INTRODUCTION

Teaching young people to always strive for beauty and live according to these rules of beauty in their daily life is one of the practical signs of refinement education.

Refinement education is teaching students to perceive and correctly understand beauty in reality, in art and nature, in people's social and labor relations, as well as in their lives, to develop their artistic taste, to instill love for beauty, and to educate their abilities to bring beauty to life. "Having a delicate taste, being able to understand and appreciate beauty, understanding artistic culture, in short, being able to see one's life based on the laws of beauty are the most necessary qualities of a perfect person. A person's understanding of beauty does not arise suddenly, but it is formed under the influence of society, people, and the environment.

Refinement education has a great impact on moral image, positive behavior, development of qualities, development of creative abilities in a person. Teaching of music, fine arts, and literature in educational institutions helps to effectively establish aesthetic education. By organizing aesthetic education in the family and in educational institutions, aesthetic interest, aesthetic need, aesthetic feeling, aesthetic taste, aesthetic judgment, aesthetic consciousness, aesthetic ideal, aesthetic vision and aesthetic activity skills are formed in students [U.I. Inoyatov, N.A. Muslimov, D.I. Roziyeva, M.H. Usmonboeva. TDPU in the name of Nizomi, 2016. B. 65-66.].

On the basis of musical heritage, creativity, sophistication, observation, musical taste, musical culture, formation of initiative, enrichment of the world of impressions, and expansion of the

scope of thinking are of great importance in young people. It can be seen that many important and significant researches have been carried out in this direction as a result of the scientific-research works on music pedagogy in our country and the republics of the Commonwealth of Independent States. In the main majority of such works, musical works, the role of the ideas presented in them in the development of the individual, the heritage of folk music, songs, folklore and classical music are studied.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A number of scientists in the field of musical-aesthetic education in our republic - Sh. Janaydarov, F. Joraev, Q. Mamirov, M. Nabieva, Kh. Nurmatov, Z. Rahimova, D. Rozieva, R. Kadirov, A. Hasanov, developed the aesthetic culture of the individual. Russian philosophers on formation by means of art - Yu. Borev, A. Burov, N. Leizerov, A. Losev, M. Kagan, V. Kanikovskiy, psychologists L. S. Vygotsky, S. Rubinstein, P. Jacobson and others, pedagogy B. Likhachev, A. Makarenko, V. Sukhomlinskyi, S.T. Shatskyi's scientific and research works in this direction are noteworthy. In their scientific-pedagogical activities, the conditions and pedagogical foundations of aesthetic education, figurative acceptance of the formation of artistic taste, problems of increasing students' interest and activity on the basis of artistic-aesthetic tools in classes and extracurricular education were studied [Karimova D.A., Khanazarova R. 2018, 7. – B. 33.].

All types of art are important in the cultivation of high artistic taste, and each of them has its own characteristics and possibilities. Implementation of aesthetic education in the educational institutions of our country is an important branch of preparing the necessary ground for the formation of high aesthetic artistic taste in students and instilling the aesthetic essence of works of art in young people. In this regard, it is one of the most important tasks to pay special attention to the musical information of students, to arm them with musical knowledge in accordance with the requirements of the program, to achieve thorough assimilation of knowledge and information about music.

Results and discussion

Plato (Plato) expresses his own ideas about art and its aesthetic essence. He divides art into two general groups. The first is imitative art (painting, sculpture, dance, music, etc.). The second group is applied art (architecture, agricultural art, medical art, political art, etc.) [Losev A.F., 1980. – S. 439.].

The pure arts of the first group draw the perceiver away from the first image, and the production arts of the second group, on the contrary, draw the person towards the first image. Because the principles of creation in pure art are taken from that side of proportion and rhythm, and its content from that side. Production arts, on the other hand, are notable for being based on principles of active creativity close to the original Creator, rather than an imitative, soulful vision of the world of things like pure art. Among the pure arts, only music belongs to Him (Allah) in its content, since it consists entirely of proportion and rhythm. That's why the great philosopher emphasizes that the educational value of music is stronger than all the arts and connects it with morality: it teaches a person to understand and love the One and Only. Plato thinks like most ancient thinkers: the pure arts, though based on pure imitation, cannot be called active. So, according to Plato, art is the first step in reaching the intellectual world. Plato's neo-Platonic aesthetics is distinguished by its analysis of beauty and art in connection with the Absolute, and is of great importance as the most remarkable spiritual phenomenon in ancient aesthetics.

The aesthetic culture of society means the set of material and spiritual values accumulated by mankind throughout the history of its development. The aesthetic culture of the student's personality is formed as a result of his active, creative assimilation of the cultural heritage of the society. Aesthetic culture is constantly changing as a result of the interaction of the person with beauty, as well as the interaction of certain qualities of the person.

Aesthetic culture is comprehensive and represents the system of attitudes and values associated with aesthetic activity. Aesthetic culture is a part of society's culture, and its content is characterized by the development of art and aesthetic relations. Aesthetic attitude and the system of aesthetic values corresponding to it are stable elements of aesthetic culture. The aesthetic goal in art, beauty and perfection, is the only goal. Due to the activity of aesthetic culture manifested through art, it can educate a person, challenge him, awaken his thoughts, affect his feelings, make him laugh or cry. Artistic culture is the core of aesthetic culture. The structure of aesthetic culture is multi-layered and includes aesthetic consciousness, aesthetic moments, and aesthetic education. In the conditions of national independence, the importance of aesthetic culture, like all elements of spiritual culture, increases [Mannopov S. 2004. – B. 6.]. The main components of the aesthetic culture of a person are aesthetic consciousness, perception, emotions, needs, relationships and aesthetic activities. Aesthetic consciousness includes aesthetic perception, knowledge, reasoning, debate, aesthetic ideal.

Aesthetic needs and relationships are first of all expressed in the aesthetic interests, tastes, and aesthetic feelings of a person. Therefore, we found it permissible to dwell on some concepts related to aesthetics.

Aesthetic consciousness is formed in the process of direct communication with social reality, nature, art, as a result of theories, views, artistic education and upbringing. Aesthetic perception is the basis of aesthetic consciousness.

Aesthetic perception is the reflection of the aesthetic essence of objects and events in the surrounding reality together with all their components. That is, it is the process of comparing perceived things with emotional and mental things that are present in the person. Aesthetic perception occurs when we encounter beauty and is characterized by a clear goal orientation.

Aesthetic reasoning is expressed in the mental movement of a person expressing his attitude to a specific aesthetic rule. A person's aesthetic judgment is characterized by its depth, refinement, complexity, high or low. The level of aesthetic judgment depends on a person's behavior and level of knowledge, aesthetic experience.

Aesthetic needs increase interest in aesthetic information. Aesthetic interest is a feature of choice that is manifested in a person's desire for aesthetic activity, collecting and collecting works of art that he likes, repeatedly reading and understanding them, trying to express an opinion about those works, being interested in knowing the opinion of others on this issue, preferring a certain artist, genre, direction, etc. is represented by the existence.

Aesthetic taste is a complex phenomenon that is formed in a person as a result of the combination of his personal and social characteristics. Aesthetic taste is formed through the flow of aesthetic information, a set of aesthetic and moral standards, and is clearly manifested in the aesthetic evaluation of objects and events by a person.

Aesthetic feeling is the experience of a person's aesthetic assessment of an object or event. The aesthetic sense helps the student to observe the shape, color and content of this item [Karimova D.A. 2008. – B. 80-98.].

In the process of musical education, the students' interest and passion for the art of music increases, on the basis of music classes, they develop their emotions and perception, sing songs, listen to music enthusiastically, and analyze the works. It should be noted that the main goal of musical education is to form the sophistication and taste of our students through artistic works. Further observations indicate that most of our young people do not have enough information about sophistication and taste. The education of sophistication plays a major role in the implementation of these issues.

Refinement education (aesthetic education) is to teach students to perceive and correctly understand the beauty in reality, in art and nature, in the social and labor relations of people, as well as in their lives, to develop their artistic taste, to instill love for beauty, and to educate the ability to bring beauty to life. Having a delicate taste, being able to understand and appreciate beauty, understanding artistic culture, in short, being able to see one's life based on the laws of beauty are the most necessary qualities of a perfect person. A person's understanding of beauty does not arise suddenly, but it is formed under the influence of society, people, and the environment. Accordingly, the laws of human artistic development are connected with the laws of social development [Karimova D.A., Khanazarova R. 2018, 7. – B. 33.].

Music education is one of the main and complex aspects of the education of sophistication, which teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the surrounding beauty. Arms with high taste and forms a spiritual outlook. Also, it has the ability to have a strong impact on human emotions, it is a proven means of moral and ideological education of young people. Sheikh Saadi, the grandfather of our national culture, did not say for nothing: "Music is the companion of the human soul" [<https://www.namhaqiqat.uz/madaniyat/Musiqa>].

Music is a form of art that occupies a wide place in our cultural life and is of great importance in the development of human personality. Music education is one of the main and complex aspects of the education of sophistication and teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around. Music equips a person with high taste and forms a spiritual outlook. Music has the ability to have a strong impact on human emotions, and is an important means of introducing students to the world of sophistication and ideological and moral education. The grandfather of our national culture, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, said, "This science is useful for the health of the body". 1995. – B. 19.]

Professor Tilab Mahmudov in his book on "Aesthetic taste" says: "A person with low taste becomes passive in life. His feelings do not seek true beauty, his taste is poor. The feeling of beauty is such a powerful feeling that it makes a person several times higher, more noble", wrote [Mahmudov T. 1964. - B. 16].

Forming sophistication in students through singing in music culture classes is a requirement of the present time. One of the main goals of music education is the formation of sophistication in students, which is a component of human spiritual culture.

The education of sophistication in the education of young students through singing is of particular importance. In the past, scholars from Turkestan gave a high value to education of sophistication. Abu Nasr Farabi, one of the great representatives of medieval philosophy, created a new stage in the history of the refined thoughts. In his "Essence of Matters", he glorified man: "Man differs from all other animals by his important characteristics... Man has the power of reason. When a person develops mental power, with its help, a person thinks,

differentiates between the beautiful and the bad, "said [Ibragimova Sh.B. Ways to develop sophistication in students through singing.]

The music sounds simultaneously epic, lyrical, and dramatic, due to its expressive nature, it tends to be more lyrical, and lyricism forms the aesthetic basis of music. Music directly reflects humanitarian aspirations. He is able to show the most beautiful qualities in a person through a beautiful melody. Music is a performing art. The French writer O. Balzac says: "the art of music comes to life only in the process of its performance, enters the language" [Nurullayeva Z.S. 2023. – B. 500-504.]

The true source of beauty is nature. Sophistication, the main goal of education is for a person to feel and enjoy the beauty of nature and society. Music, with its characteristics and unrepeatability, elevates a person spiritually, helps to form a worldview, and leads him to goodness. In particular, the aesthetic and educational potential of Uzbek national music is very great. In school music culture classes, teaching students to educate students in sophistication fulfills an important function (task): it increases the emotional compassion and aesthetic activity of a person, forms artistic taste in him, helps to study the environment in depth [Fayzieva O. and others. 1992. - B. 13.]

A specially organized activity is required to form a musical-aesthetic culture in students. In this case, the musical material should be selected and organized in such a way that it contains musical works of different nations and Uzbek composers, which have the features of national beauty and are clearly written. Such examples of musical works increase student activity, develop musical perception skills, and deepen the ability to understand various features of the musical language. All this makes it possible to further enrich musical perception and imagination, to consciously accept the means of expression inherent in music.

In fact, it is an independent requirement to educate students with sophistication and intelligence, to enjoy the benefits of enlightenment, and to educate them in the spirit of universal values through singing. For this, first of all, the teacher himself must have such great qualities. This puts a lot of responsibility on him. Therefore, it is important to radically reform today's teacher education sector, get rid of the ideological views and prejudices of the past, actively participate in raising the educational process to the level of world-developed education, and form positive feelings in the hearts and minds of students. It should be emphasized that the education of sophistication in young students is initially formed in the family, in kindergartens, at musical events, and artistic evenings. The stronger the foundation of education, the more the student's outlook on moral qualities will develop. A building built only if the foundation is strong will stand for centuries. Therefore, we can form education of sophistication in students through musical melodies and folk songs. School music culture lessons are by their very nature lessons of beauty and sophistication, a lesson that effectively enriches the spiritual world of students. Each lesson is performed with a repertoire of well-chosen works for singing and listening, with effective methods and tools to achieve the commonality of education and upbringing in the lesson, and finally, with the diligent efforts of the teacher who leads the young students to the world of sophistication through art and guides them to spiritual maturity. , achieves the goal he set for himself [Yarashev J., Murotova D. 2021.]

The art of music illuminates human life with its beauty. No other form of art can directly and powerfully affect human emotions like music. Music is a powerful tool that educates the spiritual world of human life. Without music, it is difficult for a person to feel the beauty,

emotions, and spiritual values of the world. Classical music is considered to be the pinnacle of musical art and has stood the test of time. Over the centuries, classical music lovers have not diminished. Everyone can get spiritual nourishment from the vast world of classical music. Someone admires the works of Mozart or Bach, someone enjoys the music of Tchaikovsky [National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. 12 volumes 2003. - B. 632.].

So, music is a tool that actively develops emotional feelings that quickly affects a person. A person gets acquainted with music through his mother and enjoys music. Music is an integral part of the human psyche. Education of musical culture, which is a component of human spirituality, is the main goal of music education. To realize this higher goal, the music teacher has the following tasks:

1. To increase students' interest and love for the art of music.
2. Development of artistic creativity and feelings in the process of musical activity.
3. Ethical and aesthetic education of students through the artistic and ideological content of the works.
4. In music lessons, it is necessary to do things like awakening enthusiasm in students regarding profession and work.

The implementation of these goals and tasks depends on the professional skills and ethics of the teacher. A music teacher should be a highly cultured, broad-minded person who loves his profession and children. He should have deep knowledge of pedagogy, psychology, children's physiology, theory of ethics and aesthetics, practical areas of music theory, music teaching methodology [Azizov O. 2022. - B. 55-58.].

Music culture is not only a song, a learned science, but at the same time it is a theoretical and practical basis of national moral, national-ideological, ideological education. Organization of musical culture lessons in an unconventional way based on the needs of the times, in interesting situations for students, teaches them to think, search, find new ideas as a mature generation and has a strong impact on their national spiritual education. If the idea of organizing music lessons based on the types of education of a perfect person is based on students' free thinking, free assessment and exchange of ideas based on questions and answers, the lesson of music culture will have an interesting and impressive content.

Artistic education is mainly manifested through socio-aesthetic ideals. The education of sophistication is, first of all, the artistic education of artistic feelings in everyone [Cathrine Sadolin. 2012. - R. 58-69. www.sompletevocalinstitute.com]. Such high sophistication should not be taken to mean that it is devoid of intelligence. These two sides complement each other in the formation of a person as a complete person. In a real work of art, emotion and perception merge with deep ideological and intellectual content. The education of sophistication is the education of the senses with the mind, or more precisely, the education of the mind with the medium of the senses. These two sides are inextricably linked.

In the process of growing sophistication, taste, feelings and skills based on a scientific worldview, a person becomes spiritually richer and nobler, and his life becomes more meaningful. Every person's love for the time in which he lives increases. All this forms and further develops the ability to feel and know beauty in every person. A truly refined taste means the ability to enjoy real beauty, the need to perceive and create sophistication in work, life, behavior, and art.

Apathy destroys a person's positive attitude towards reality. As a result, he begins to look indifferent to sophistication. Sophistication education is important today, because taste,

perception and prudence have become a vital need for every person in work, production, and daily practical activities. Sometimes in life we meet people with low taste and spiritual poverty. In order to hide their mental, moral and spiritual weakness, such people make fake behavior, do things that do not suit them, dress in bad taste, listen to music and chants that are not fun and noisy. When you observe such people, you will see that they are indifferent people who do not work hard and are indifferent to the worries of life.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, in practice, the full implementation of the tasks of aesthetic education forms such qualities as initiative, creativity, foresight, aspiration, and the ability to dream in students. A society that educates students who are mentally mature, physically healthy, morally pure, and have a sense of national responsibility will develop stably. Summarizing the opinions mentioned above, it should be said that the songs, tunes, and audio recording during music listening lessons show the wide range of possibilities of music art in making the young generation a mature person in all respects.

References:

1. U.I. Inoyatov, N.A. Muslimov, D.I. Rozieva, M.H. Usmonboeva Pedagogy: a textbook for non-pedagogical higher education institutions. - Tashkent: TDPU named after Nizomi, 2016. - B. 65-66. (- 256 p.)
2. Karimova D.A., Khanazarova R. Current issues facing the science of "musical culture" in the aesthetic education of students. Modern education / Sovremennoe obrazovanie. 2018, 7. - B. 33.
3. Лосев А.Ф. История античной эстетики. Поздний эллинизм. - М.: Искусства, 1980. - С. 439.
4. Mannopov S. Uzbek folk music culture (Textbook). - Tashkent: "New Age Generation", 2004. - B. 6.
5. Karimova D.A. Fundamentals of musical pedagogical skills. - T.: "Economy-finance", 2008. - B. 80-98.
6. Karimova D.A., Khanazarova R. Current issues facing the science of "Music culture" in the aesthetic education of students. Modern education / Sovremennoe obrazovanie. 2018, 7. - B. 33.
7. <https://www.namhaqiqat.uz/madaniyat/> Musiqa – odam ruhiyatining yo‘ldoshi
8. Yoldoshev J. "Development of music education and education in Uzbekistan". - Tashkent, 1995. - B. 19.
9. Mahmudov T. About aesthetic taste. - T.: "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 1964. - B. 16.
10. Ibragimova Sh.B. Ways to develop sophistication in students through singing. file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/Ibragimova+Shakhnoza+Bakhodirovna
11. Nurullayeva Z.S. Uniqueness of music as an aesthetic activity. National University of Uzbekistan Volume 4 NUU Conference 2 | 2023. - B. 500-504.
12. Fayzieva O. and others. Ways of forming education of musical sophistication in students. - T., 1992. - B. 13.
13. Yarashev J., Murotova D. Music teaching methodology. Study guide. - Bukhara: "Durdona" publishing house, 2021.

14. National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. 12 roofs. T.: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2003. - B. 632.
15. Azizov O. Strengthening of students' knowledge and skills in music lessons. Society and innovations - Obshchestvo i innovatsii - Society and innovations. Special Issue – 08. 2022. – B. 55-58.
16. Cathrine Sadolin. Complete vocal technique. 2012. – P. 58-69.
www.completevocalinstitute.com

